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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, VIc.
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Improved STDDBL photometry

The photometric solution results reported in NDAC/LO/108 (Paper VIb) are unfortunately erroneous due to a program bug affecting the majority of the runs with separation less than 10 arcsec. These solutions have now been remade, and most of the systematic errors very pleasingly disappear. (The astrometry is also virtually unchanged).

The colour-equation (1) in Paper VIb is only changed a little, to

$$dm_1 = -0.045 + 0.082 * (B - V)_{pr} \quad (1)$$

and the residual spread is now down at half the formal mean error (?). For the relative magnitudes, there is a corresponding relation

$$d(dm) = -0.003 + 0.10 * d(B - V) \quad (1a)$$

where $d(B - V)$ is now the colour-difference (sec-pr). (In the present simulations, a certain relation is found only for separations less than 10 arcsec, where it reduces the mean residual spread from 1.5 to 1.1 times the formal mean errors. Ideally, we should have the same slope in eqs (1) and (1a), and it should apply also for larger separations with individual IFOV-pointing. There is a great 'observational' uncertainty, however, because a large difference in (B-V) corresponds to a faint secondary with a poorly determined magnitude).

Equations (2) and (3) in Paper VIb are *not* valid, being due to a missing correction for the photocentric IFOV-pointing. When working as intended, STDDBL automatically corrects for each star's mean distance from the IFOV centre (giving a diminished effective intensity), and the IFOV pointing strategy should have no influence on the photometry. (Also, the apparently deviating results in Paper VIa are correct).

In conclusion, we see that the STDDBL photometry is rather free from systematic effects other than the well-understood colour-equations above. The post-reduction calibrations will therefore hopefully be somewhat simpler than might be feared.